

THE IMPACT OF MICRO AND SMALL BUSINESS MORTALITY ON THE MICROECONOMICS

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ABSTRACT

This paper addresses the issue of “the main causes of mortality in micro and small businesses”. Its scientific relevance lies in the fact that this subject is still little discussed and the knowledge that is achieved is far from what actually happens. In this sense, this paper aims to clarify some points that are unclear in this area. Its social relevance lies in the fact that this research may help to understand the reasons that usually lead micro and small businesses to premature bankruptcy and thus guide other entrepreneurs to take due care when preparing their projects and opening new organizations. Micro and small businesses have intensified their position even in the absence of support proportional to their economic participation. Micro and small businesses, in general, are more versatile in terms of adaptability to internal professional markets. This is because their production, in terms of volume and operating costs, is much lower than that of a large company, which allows them to reduce the operating volume without significantly affecting the total profitability of their assets. Even so, it does not reduce the bankruptcy rates of micro and small businesses for a variety of reasons, from the lack of an effective management process to the lack of resources to maintain the business. This paper aims to present the reasons why small businesses die prematurely and some ways to avoid such situations. Micro and small businesses in Brazil correspond to the vast majority of Brazilian companies, and are responsible for a significant portion of the GDP – Gross Domestic Product. The general objective is to deepen theoretical and technical knowledge about small businesses, so that the main difficulties and problems faced, as well as the difficulties encountered by small and micro businesses and what they need to develop in order to be successful, can be identified. The specific objectives are to conduct a brief study about small businesses in order to identify and develop appropriate strategies to reduce their mortality.

Keywords: Mortality of Micro and Small Enterprises; Strategic Planning; Competitive Advantages and Disadvantages of SMEs.

INTRODUCTION

Micro and small enterprises (MSEs) represent the greatest economic force of any nation, and this is without any exaggeration, because they take care of serving a wider public and their production of goods and services is done in a localized manner and for specific targets. Unlike large and macro organizations, these work in an environment where the attraction for large production vehicles does not want to approach.

According to Oliveira & Simoneti (2013), micro and small companies have limitations, among which the one that holds them back the most, sometimes preventing them from making major advances, is the financial issue and issues related to personnel, which characterizes them as a factor of competitive disadvantage, as they cannot have a contingent of highly qualified professionals with greater availability of time to invest in market research and development of differentiated products and services.

The authors cited above also argue that, with reference to people management, the human potential of these organizations is compromised, due to the fact that a single person performs multiple tasks, which prevents specialization in a given sector. What cannot be denied is that micro and small businesses are of vital importance to the country's economy (Id.).

What this study sought to do was to bring to the field of academic discussion a way of knowing some possible reasons that lead micro and small businesses to bankruptcy and to close their doors, ending their economic and commercial activities in such a short time. It is important to consider that no business is born as a product of decline, that is, an entire structure is conjectured, an idea of prosperity and economic growth and the opening of new market niches or even a specialization in the sector in which it operates, directly or indirectly.

In the social environment and even in the scientific-academic environment, there is much speculation about why micro and small businesses go bankrupt, but at no time do these explanations satisfy the desire for answers that flood the agents in the field of Administration. Therefore, we started with a bibliographical investigation that translated into simple and accessible language the concept of micro and small businesses, as well as their classification, as given by development agencies and specialized technicians, to then seek, through more in-depth research, to list the physical and subjective elements that involve such organizations and from this point reach a conclusion about the possible causes of the mortality of micro and small businesses.

The study is structured in such a way as to allow the understanding, analysis and interpretation of data in a clear and objective manner, through a logical cadence that presents

bibliographic data through systematic study. The understanding that, at first, is that there is lack of managerial structure in the way such organizations are managed and planned. The lack of material and financial resources is not the final impediment to their downfall; rather, there is a lack of planning in all areas, especially when it comes to *strategic planning* .

The aim of this study is to present means capable of promoting clarification on the main technical and managerial points (tangible and intangible) on the mortality of micro and small companies, based on the premise that clarification on these could lead to more in-depth studies on them and the causes of their early openings and closures, as well as organizing forms of intervention so that such an event, the premature closure of their business activities, does not occur.

DEFINITION AND CLASSIFICATION OF MICRO AND SMALL ENTERPRISES

According to La Rovere (2000), there is no consensus regarding the criteria used to classify companies as micro, small, medium or large in Brazil. The most widely used method is quantitative, which uses annual gross revenue and the number of employees as a basis for classifying the company's size.

The most commonly used definition to classify Micro and Small Businesses is that found in General Law No. 9,841, of October 5, 1999. According to this law, companies that have an annual turnover of up to R\$240,000.00 (Two hundred and forty thousand reais) are classified as micro businesses. Small businesses must have a turnover between R\$240,000.01 (Two hundred and forty thousand reais and one cent) and R\$2,400,000.00 (Two million and four hundred thousand reais) annually to be classified in this category.

According to Fortes (2014), classification is generally based on the number of employees and most defining entities establish microenterprises as those with up to 10 employees; small enterprises as those with up to 100 employees.

Another classification criterion is revenue. The classification would be linked to the volume of resources obtained during the period of one year. However, this same classification may vary depending on the sectors examined, ranging from the extraction and treatment of minerals, to the different types of companies (metallurgy, transportation, furniture, cardboard, chemical, food, printing, *etc.* , for example) (FORTES, 2014, p. 03).

Another definition used by the Brazilian Micro and Small Business Support Service (SEBRAE) is that micro-enterprises are those that employ up to 9 (nine) people in the case of

commerce and services, or up to 19 (nineteen) in the case of the industrial or construction sectors. Small businesses are those that employ 10 (ten) to 49 (forty-nine) people in the case of commerce and services, and 20 (twenty) to 99 (ninety-nine) people in the case of industry and construction companies.

Federal government agencies such as the National Bank for Economic and Social Development (BNDES) use another parameter to classify the size of the company and grant credits : micro-enterprises must have annual gross revenue of up to R\$1,200,000.00 (one million two hundred thousand reais); and small companies must have gross revenue greater than R\$1,200,000.00 (one million two hundred thousand reais) and less than R\$10,500,000.00 (ten million five hundred thousand reais).

Table 1: Classification of Companies by Size, according to various bodies.

Institution	Classification by Company Size			
	Microenterprise		Small business	
SEBRAE	Sector	No. of Employees	Sector	No. of Employees
	Industry and Civil Construction	Up to 19 employees	Industry and Civil Construction	From 20 to 99 employees
	Trade and Service	Up to 09 employees	Trade and Service	From 10 to 49 employees
Simples Nacional and General Law of SMEs	Legal Type	Invoicing	Legal Type	Invoicing
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Individual entrepreneur; Business (commercial) society; Simple (civil) society. 	Annual gross revenue equal to or less than R\$240,000.00	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Individual entrepreneur; Business (commercial) company; Simple (civil) company. 	Annual gross revenue greater than R\$240,000.00 and equal to or less than R\$2,400,000.00
BNDES	Invoicing		Invoicing	
	Annual or annualized gross operating revenue less than or equal to R\$1,200 thousand (one million and two hundred thousand Reais)		Annual gross operating revenue exceeding R\$1,200 thousand (one million two hundred thousand Reais) and less than or equal to R\$10,500 thousand (ten million five hundred thousand Reais)	

Source: Marques and Sousa, 2009.

According to Fortes (2014), micro and small businesses emerge from the conditions to which the economy has been subjected in recent times, in which salary and employment

conditions have become insufficient to maintain the demands of daily life. In other words, as a way of escaping the conditions of underemployment and low wages, a new class of entrepreneurs has emerged who do not have the slightest technical-theoretical preparation to run a business or ways of raising funds to maintain the enterprise.

The concept used in this work to define and classify micro and small businesses is in accordance with the definition of the Brazilian Micro and Small Business Support Service (SEBRAE).

THE IMPACT OF MICRO AND SMALL ENTERPRISES ON THE ECONOMY

According to Martins (2005), from the 1980s onwards, micro and small businesses began to be valued. Because they were less vulnerable to market changes, SMEs began to gain space in the market. The same author also states that the small business segment is one of the main pillars of support of the national economy, not only by the number of establishments and distribution geographically and for its capacity to generate jobs. Although its socioeconomic importance is recognized, the sector finds several obstacles to its development, sustainability and competitiveness.

Since the 1990s, large companies established in Brazil, following a global trend, have encouraged the process of outsourcing areas that are not considered essential to their business. Thus, more and more security and general cleaning companies began to emerge. According to SEBRAE, smaller companies have opted to hire micro and small companies to avoid the extremely high labor costs, since an employee can cost up to 120% more than their monthly salary. The Statute of Micro and Small Companies in Brazil, from 1998, began to facilitate this business policy.

Setting up your own business is the most common dream among Brazilian employees, but being an entrepreneur of a micro or small business is an activity that still presents several bureaucratic barriers.

Micro and small businesses have great socioeconomic importance in Brazil with regard to the distribution of jobs and income. According to data from SEBRAE (2005), micro and small businesses represent 99.2% of all existing companies in Brazil and employ around 60% of the economically active population. active, being responsible for 36.34% of jobs and micro-enterprises for 23.66%, generating revenue of approximately 20% of Brazilian GDP.

According to data from SEBRAE (2019), approximately 460,000 new companies emerge in Brazil each year, the vast majority of which are micro and small businesses. The

largest types of concentrations are in the areas of services and commerce, with 80% of micro and small businesses operating in this sector.

ECONOMIC VIABILITIES OF MICRO AND SMALL ENTERPRISES

Motta and Pereira (1986) state that the modern world is marked by the replacement of small companies by large bureaucratic companies, characterized by rationality, large-scale production, formalism, depersonalization, professionalism and the search for efficiency.

This idea that large companies would dominate the business world was a reality until the 1970s, when there was a strong growth of micro and small companies after the economic crisis of the 1970s and 1980s, which occurred in several countries that adopted the industrial development model based on mass production. During this period, large companies that were the basis for economic development in the industrialized world underwent processes of streamlining their structures, divided their structure into smaller units and outsourced some activities in an attempt to adapt to the demands of the new economy that was unfolding, based on liberal capital (MOTTA, 2000). After this period, the importance of micro and small companies in the economic scenario was reviewed.

According to Longenecker *et al* (1997), micro and small businesses, as part of the broader business community, contribute to the economic well-being and development of the nation by producing a portion of the total goods and services. In addition, they have some qualities that end up offering exceptional contributions, as they offer many opportunities for formal, direct and indirect employment for a population and an economy in rapid growth: while large companies are flattening and laying off employees, micro and small businesses continue to generate jobs (Id.).

This is because their production method is, in many and diverse aspects, artisanal, following volume standards and conditions that are not compatible with the needs of a large wholesaler. They produce for specific markets with very varied needs, which justifies the low investment. They introduce innovations: innovative activity tends to decrease as the level of production concentration in a given sector increases, hence confirming the importance of these companies, which stimulate productivity by providing better products and production methods.

Because they have relatively lower operating costs compared to large companies, micro and small businesses can venture into specific professional markets without running too many risks, because their profit margin can be calculated based on eccentricity and exclusivity and

not on exponential volumes. They stimulate competition, acting as economic competitors, and have a healthy effect on the capitalist system.

When there is a sense of fair competition between partners, the customer benefits because there is a greater regional distribution of basic necessities and the provision of specialized services, which promotes broad conditions of choice. They assist large companies by: performing some functions efficiently, such as the distribution function, connecting products and customers, and the supply function, which allows them to act as direct suppliers and also as subcontractors, contributing to the success of sales and service for large companies. In this, they can act as contractors or subcontractors for large corporations in the direct and indirect provision of services, which would be unfeasible for them from an economic and logistical point of view (storage and distribution). They produce goods and services efficiently: being less affected by complex structures, which inhibit the flexibility and productivity of many organizations, they are efficient and show that being bigger does not necessarily mean being better (LONGENECKER *et al.* , 1997).

In this regard, it must be considered that the quality control services of a *holding company* are, without any conditions of comparison, indisputably better than those of a small or micro-company, however, the ease of exchanging and replacing services makes the latter more competitive and ends up, in many cases, attracting the preference of customers.

Thus, the importance of micro and small businesses in terms of economic viability goes far beyond providing complementary activities for large companies. They have a degree of specialization in various fields of activity and can, in many cases, be competitive.

According to the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE) (2001) and the Annual Report of Social Information of the Ministry of Labor and Employment (RAIS/TEM), in Brazil there are approximately 3.5 million companies, of which 98% are micro and small companies. It was identified that the activities of micro and small companies maintain approximately 35 million people employed throughout the country, that is, 59% of Brazilian workers (this calculation also includes individual companies).

COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF SMEs

With the advent of globalization, competition for different market niches has become more intense and companies have to adapt to the different modes of change that encompass consumer behavior, habits, new opportunities, desires, economic conditions of each organization and the ability to adapt to all these market nuances.

Micro and small businesses, in general, are more versatile in terms of adaptability to domestic professional markets. This is because their production, in terms of volume and operating costs, are much lower than those of a large company, which allows them to reduce operating volume without significantly affecting the total profitability of their assets.

According to Silva (2004), small businesses have demonstrated flexibility in establishing organizational arrangements, valuing simple structures, which become more dynamic, with greater capacity for innovation and more sensitive to market demands, providing personalized service to consumers. These companies are also characterized by the creation of jobs, the provision of opportunities for entrepreneurship, the capacity for diversification of products and processes, providing greater competitiveness and facilitating cooperation between stakeholders, especially producers, traders and consumers.

Micro and small businesses are generally family-owned; as a result, decisions are made in a timely manner, without depending on a board of directors or shareholders' meeting, a situation that demands time and often limits their actions and conditions for making decisions.

This business segment has its prerogatives in a format that facilitates its actions inside and outside its home. This gives it an advantage over macro-businesses; and, in return, the need for business expansion is subject to interventions given the limited access to credit, financing and market reach that requires large volumes of production of goods and services.

COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGES OF MICRO AND SMALL ENTERPRISES

Besanko, Drannove and Shanley (2000) define competitive advantage in terms of the firm's optimal result in the combined use of its resources. This definition corresponds to the resulting competitive advantage, that is, that which results from the combined effects of the various factors that affect the company's performance.

This definition is directly related to macro companies and *holdings*, which may have a direct and considerable volume of capital, willing to invest in infrastructure improvements and counting on the support of advertising and complex and intense marketing mechanisms, which makes the investment in possibilities of new profits and not in direct costs.

Therefore, talking about advantages is a very delicate subject because it always involves comparisons with other systems. A micro-enterprise has the advantage of operating in simple or easy-to-operate systems, because its field of operation is limited to a radius very close to its installation site, therefore, the logistical dimensioning, customers and opportunities are in the areas of financial limitation.

Another advantage of these companies is the decision-making process that does not depend on large meetings or even disregarding such systems because, most of the time, the CEO is directly involved in the functions of direct manager of the system, making decisions and/or serving customers.

According to Fortes (2014),

The type of administration of these units is similar to that of the company itself, when the owner (CEO and founder) exercises a single-person and authoritarian management, coordinating the operational areas and making all the decisions. In order to develop, he implements a real division of labor and begins the search for qualified professionals to direct and manage it (FORTES, 2014, p.05).

Another advantage is the ability to serve various market niches that have become increasingly specific, such as the kitchen, cosmetics, food product distribution, perishables and even smaller communities. Physical proximity to consumers reveals a context of trust and credibility that can and is explored and developed by micro and small businesses. Unlike large retail chains, which are able to satisfy part of the needs of today's Brazilian consumer, especially in terms of price, diversity and payment methods, i.e., cost-benefit of consumption.

However, selling is an interactive action full of symbolism; the interaction between supplier and consumer is part of the product. This interaction is precarious in retail sales, where self-service processes are minimally interactive. On the other hand, micro and small businesses add the perspective of the social relationship involved in consumption, and, although the action of making the sale itself is the same regardless of the size of the enterprise, the purchase would not be made in a supermarket, but in the market of my neighbor, who lives in the same neighborhood, who knows the clientele by name, knows their children and who supports the same soccer team as his client. In other words, there is a direct and subjective identification of the product with the subject; the person begins to represent the mini-market and this enterprise, in turn, is alive and has a personality (FORTES, 2014).

All this is due to the fact that with the structural changes in the conditions of locomotion and logistics of various products, it is no longer so interesting for micro-enterprises to be involved in situations where operations tend to be fruitless or with unsatisfactory results from an economic point of view. They can serve markets focused on the third and fourth sectors, with greater chances of success and this is not only advantageous for large companies, because their technical assistance and advisory and/or consulting conditions can be met with the due quality certificate that the brand supports in its *Know-how*, without travel costs, social security and security expenses. For micro-enterprises, which become service providers, the advantages

are to have their names directly linked to large corporations that guarantee them access to first-rate, superior quality services and consumer goods, given the quality control system of large corporations.

The agility with which micro and small businesses deal with market adversities puts them at the forefront, enabling them to be at the forefront of economic development and survival conditions. In terms of direct job creation, they have an advantage over macro businesses, due to the fact that they have smaller technological undertakings and large-scale production machinery, which sometimes makes them more competitive, considering that their operational and maintenance costs are reduced.

Flexibility refers to the ability of micro and small businesses to respond almost immediately to the demands of the specific market in which they operate by adapting their products to changes undertaken, requested and/or required by their customers. This flexibility results from less formalized structures and less specialized equipment that allow for the introduction of changes and adaptations more easily. When compared to large companies, the services provided by micro and small businesses to their customers are more specific and faster. The fact that they are closer to buyers – which is very important – and can meet smaller orders is a characteristic that greatly favors them, making them more competitive.

Forte (2014) groups together the advantages linked to micro and small companies into two large groups, highlighting in the first group those companies linked to a bureaucratic nature, such as:

Flexibility: they adapt easily to new situations and circumstances;

Mobility: they move to new lines of products or services as soon as they are required by the market;

Quick decisions: there is no waste of time in exhausting meetings and bureaucracy does not hinder decision-making;

Direct contact with customers: the border market provides a closer relationship with consumers, allowing us to quickly comply with aspects of flexibility and mobility in differentiated and constant service;

Behavioral informality: relationships are more personal and familiar, allowing for greater understanding and joint efforts;

Group feeling: is a result of behavioral informality, providing greater participation by employees in company decisions;

Low break-even point: the profit result is achieved more easily, as fixed costs are lower and variables have better conditions for reduction;

Independence and freedom of decision and action: the objectives and goals they intend to achieve are determined, defined and risked by the entrepreneurs themselves, and there should be no justifications or requests for permission from any external body;

Greater creativity and initiative: they are usually more daring, creative and open to new things;

Reduced volume of investments: with lower fixed costs, there is more capital allocated to research into new products and technologies;

Minimized overhead costs: economic obligations arising from administrative expenses, bureaucracy and intermediate services are lower (FORTE, 2014, pp. 07-08).

All these variables are directly linked to greater internal corporate bureaucracy. This facilitates decision-making and adjustments to exchange rate changes. And, in the second group, the same author lists the advantages of micro and small companies under the group that has an operational nature, such as:

Inventiveness and experimentation: serve as a testing ground for new ideas and products, new services and materials, which a large company is unable to test or does not wish to try;

Market anticipation: small managers not only follow but also anticipate the market — innovative concepts can be tested without large capital investments or consumer market development;

Attention to detail: they handle orders for different products or varieties of orders, such as small quantities of an item, with a wide variety of models;

Ease of changing plans and schedules: they follow trends more easily, especially market trends, as soon as they begin to show their strength;

Agility in the face of competition: any move by competitors is responded to through measures to reduce costs, for example, by reducing the final costs of products and/or services;

Greater control over production: with fewer tasks to schedule, the normal deadlines of the production process are modified, fulfilling extended working hours, due to the absence of intricate coordination steps required by mass production;

Ease of changing production: a simple phone call from a customer results in immediate action, as instructions do not travel through the long command channels of a large company;

Versatility: all changes characteristic of this type of undertaking are carried out quickly and at low costs (FORTE, 2014, p.08).

This facilitates decision-making and adjustments to exchange rate changes. And, in the second group, the same author, mentioned above, lists the advantages of micro and small companies under the group that has an operational nature. All these advantages of small and medium-sized companies make them remain active in the market even with a reduced capital flow, which limits the range of direct investments and with a very deficient strategic performance.

COMPETITIVE DISADVANTAGES OF MICRO AND SMALL ENTERPRISES

Micro and small businesses have invariants that often make them incapable of competing in the market in a way that could yield a possible and favorable return in the medium

and long term. This is because the operating methods within their system, especially the financial system, are managed in a way that does not allow or severely limits bolder actions to be taken without major financial risks. Such actions may be caused by fear of a sudden change in the country's economic policies or even the lack of a bias in which direct and indirect costs can be reduced in times of low demand.

Demand is characterized as one of the main biases of competitive disadvantage for micro and small businesses. The following explanation is given for this: this market situation is directly linked to the variety of products and services that can be offered to customers. Due to the low investment power of these companies, their range of options, is generally reduced, which places them at the mercy of the seasonality of the consumer market.

An example of this are micro and small businesses linked to the cutting and sewing sector. When these small and micro businesses are affiliated with large brands, there is no shortage of work, but when they operate independently, they tend to specialize in school uniforms and the greatest demand occurs in pre-determined months, when they must hire more employees, thus bearing the labor costs or redouble their efforts during the working day, which, after such a period of euphoria, returns to the set of pre-defined productions and subject to sporadic orders.

With the advent of globalization, the situations of micro and small businesses have become true paradoxes; on the one hand, the competition for markets has become fiercer while the number of entrepreneurs has grown dramatically, that is, the market economy, especially the individual one, has come to be managed by the increasingly constant risk of losses and not by the possibility of gains.

Macro companies, due to their volume of available capital and industrial-scale production capacity, sometimes obtain better price conditions and accessibility for the customer; in addition to this, there is another advantage, which is the ability to offer a variety of essential products and services, which makes competition fiercer and, at times, incompatible for small entrepreneurs.

Another competitive disadvantage of micro and small businesses is linked to investment capital. According to Forte (2014), the origin of capital in small businesses is overwhelmingly in the family economy or, when not, it comes from loans obtained through special lines of credit, or even from one of the partners. This was supposed to be understood as a factor of strength, however, doubts and disagreements arise because with the expectation of high net returns, however, incompatible with such, if the capital comes from family income, there are internal conflicts between the spouses and if it comes from one of the partners, the one who

invests feels entitled not to put as much effort into the business, since the capital invested in the company is his/hers and another obstacle is when it comes to accounting for profits and dividends, that the one who invested money is fair to have his/her share reimbursed, however, on the other hand, the one who worked at the forefront of the business, running direct risks of losses and facing creditors and other stressful situations, is more than fair to have his/her compensation due to the hours of effort he/she put in. However, it turns out that these companies are almost always the offspring of enthusiasm and passion, not of pure accounting reason, which ultimately leads to their disappearance or to their acquisition by one of the former partners.

When the source of income comes from family capital, the company becomes, *ad literans*, the owner's livelihood and, therefore, there is a very low level of reinvestment of the operating working capital, because the main concern ends up being focused on his survival and that of his dependents, when moreover, they do not participate in the business work. Even if the owner begins to think in terms of profit, more than the simple remuneration for his work, he does not do so with much confidence because the operational volume is not capable of allowing reinvestments of the order desired by the entrepreneur, making more daring actions in the elaboration of medium and long-term projects difficult (FORTE, 2014).

In micro and small businesses, the owner's relationship with the production method demonstrates a rudimentary separation between technical processes and administrative activities. In other words, everything remains at a level of guidance in which there is almost an unhealthy mix regarding the success of the enterprise, because a single individual takes care of the entire process, from the acquisition of materials to the final sale, including the production methods. Technical processes do not always follow clearly tangible standards, and health and safety standards and occupational safety are often too demanding in terms of the final costs of the product, which leads owners to evade such actions, putting the final quality of the product and the safety of workers at risk (FORTE, 2014).

In this type of company, the level of advice is very restricted, and the control systems are personal. Therefore, what should be a positive factor of competitiveness becomes a disadvantage, because it involves several employer feelings and many other intrinsic ones, since “in order to grow, it starts to require more sophisticated initial internal advice, expanding the external one, and the operational and strategic decision systems implemented allow greater delegation, based on previously considered rules” (FORTE, 2014, p. 05).

Small businesses are unable to develop products and test them in professional markets because the capital and management infrastructure for developing a project and measuring its performance is literally incompatible with their size. In other words, there are sometimes

several small businesses that develop products but are unable to test them in the external market. This is because the problem related to the area of Design and Development (R&D), for micro and small businesses, basically represents a problem of scale, as there is not enough sales volume to fund the development of new products and processes, which makes them dependent on the exploration of old products and/or the provision of services to macro-sized companies. According to Forte (2014), the mastery of a simple technology, sufficient for the manufacture of a single product, guided by the owner-director, may constitute the only research and development activity practiced in the small business, with no strong concern for improving products and processes.

Another factor that presents serious competitiveness problems for micro and small businesses is that “ *personnel management policies* are unsystematic and often paternalistic” (FORTE, 2014, p. 05). [Emphasis in the original].

This fact hinders the levels of competition and expansion, because as growth begins, the need to establish more coherent policies automatically arises, with an emphasis on stability and services provided, these based on technical criteria in operational costs, making both direct and indirect relations between sectors and means of production increasingly impersonal.

Until the advent of globalization, micro and small businesses survived in a somewhat less dangerous way, because their customers were loyal to what they knew and believed, blindly acquiring, with their purchasing power, the best that was within their reach. However, with the entry of various imported products, at much lower prices, there was an introduction of a new added value to the possession of high-end goods. As a result, these companies suffered losses in relation to macro companies, due to the volume of acquisition and revenue, obviously interfering effectively in their ability to serve a more demanding market willing to satisfy a luxury.

It is not that micro and small businesses are not in a position to meet their specific needs. What keeps them out of the powerful competitive market that has formed around business activity is the ability to offer products with the same quality and prices as others. And there is also the difference that their purchasing capacity does not allow them to significantly reduce values by purchasing in larger quantities, which could be achieved if they had greater purchasing power and inventory capacity. However, as they operate in restricted markets, there would be an accumulation of goods not in circulation, which would bring embedded expenses such as storage, insurance, and possible risks, requiring the opportunity for offers and promotions, which, in the end, could transform the marketing action into economic suicide.

Micro and small businesses have limited negotiating power due to the difficulties inherent to organizations of this size. Therefore, with regard to price, these organizations seek to meet the parameters of the market in which they operate, we emphasize once again. However, these organizations must also seek to compete in other variables that are not only focused on price, but on the added value of their products. In addition, the pricing strategy needs to consider the variable and fixed costs that these organizations have, in addition to the margin percentage that these companies aim for (OLIVEIRA & SIMONETTI, 2013, p. 09).

The aforementioned authors complement their statements by saying that for a long time, price represented the determining variable of consumer purchasing power. The market was the same and the price parameters were quite similar, and the consumer did not have much choice. However, with the increasingly rapid changes in the national and international economic context, affecting external and internal markets, that is, the local economy (both macro and micro), because they affected those who determine the real direction of each bid, *that is*, with the considered maturity of the consumer with reference to their decision-making power, organizations detected the need to change their strategies and meet this new market profile. Thus, factors such as innovation, differentiation and competitive advantage began to dictate the market rules and organizations that did not redesign their structures were left out of the market (OLIVEIRA & SIMONETTI, 2013).

The competitive disadvantages that affect micro and small businesses are directly related to the management processes chosen as the ideal way to manage them. However, what can be considered a mechanism of competitive disadvantage for a micro business can be considered an advantage for a macro business, or vice versa. The major problem related to this lies in the behavioral change of consumers in the new economic era, who have become more demanding and more susceptible to immediate dissatisfaction.

These conditions can be overcome by cooperatives that allow micro and small businesses to acquire materials for local marketing in quantity and quality at a relatively low cost. This type of operation could place them at the forefront of market competitiveness, aiming to serve a diverse audience with varied needs. To this end, there would be a need to organize the spaces in which they operate, with which products and who would be the possible direct suppliers.

Considering that competitive advantages can arise from benefits of size, privileged access to resources or even from options that guarantee strategic flexibility when competitors “may lose flexibility for institutional (legal, cultural) reasons” (GHEMAWAT, 1986, sp), the main competitive disadvantage related to micro and small companies would be in the wake of

isolated action, that is, believing in the con that they can survive, on their own, amid an increasingly frequent contingent of mergers by holding *companies* .

In the 1990s, Porter (1990) related advantage to value creation, that is, competitive advantage arises from the value that a company is able to create for its buyers and that, with such action, exceeds the company's manufacturing cost and provides the difference between the offer of one firm and that of others. Here, if taken simply by this simplistic view linked to factors of direct and indirect support to external causes such as the Environment, health conditions and service to its employees and their families, quality of raw material and packaging, micro and small companies are at the mercy of the slavery of nothing being able to offer as added value, since the cost for this is high and the return is only possible through powerful *marketing* , that is, this value would be a perfect competitive disadvantage.

CAUSES OF MORTALITY IN MICRO AND SMALL ENTERPRISES

There are many causes of mortality in micro and small businesses, but according to research carried out by SEBRAE (2004), some stand out as being the main ones due to the high rate of companies that will close for the same reasons. One of the highest rates indicated is the lack of working capital (a crucial element for the closure of companies according to entrepreneurs), followed by the lack of customers, followed by the most diverse types of financial problems, bad payers (cases of default), lack of bank credit, economic recession in the country, inadequate location, lack of managerial knowledge, problems with inspection, lack of qualified labor, inadequate facilities, high tax burden.

The difficulties and reasons for the closure of companies are divided into four categories: management failures, economic causes, operational logistics and also public policies and legal framework.

MANAGEMENT FAILURES

Among the main causes of mortality, we can identify that within management failures, working capital represents a significant portion of the problems identified in micro and small companies. One of the main causes of mortality is the lack of working capital, which is identified by Braga (1989, p. 81) “as resources applied to current assets, basically formed by inventories, accounts receivable and cash on hand.” A broader approach also includes current liabilities.

Assaf Neto (2008, p. 516) defines working capital as “the volume of capital applied by the company in its short-term operating cycle, which takes different forms throughout its production and sales process.”

According to SEBRAE (2013), working capital management is one of the most important aspects for the company's financial health, because when the company is unable to maintain a satisfactory level of cash to honor its commitments due to working capital imbalance, it will probably be forced to leave the market, especially if it loses credit with suppliers and banks.

What companies are looking for most these days is to improve working capital management, as it is through good management that they can increase business profits, obtain bank credit, and invest in the company's growth.

SEBRAE (2011) describes the main financial problems faced by micro and small businesses as: cash shortages, lack of working capital, wrong prices, high costs, exaggerated investments and default.

According to Matias and Lopes Júnior (2002), financial management is responsible in many cases for the failure of micro and small companies and, in small companies, it assumes a fundamental and essential role, since this type of company generally does not operate with relative financial flexibility or sufficient assets as guarantees to offer to financial institutions to obtain resources.

According to the authors, in micro and small companies, the role of financial administrator is normally performed by the owner, who, due to having too many responsibilities, ends up not performing this role adequately, in addition to not having the time or qualified personnel available to perform this role.

Miranda (2003) emphasizes that a cost system, when well organized and appropriate to the company's direct objectives, which is accurate and up-to-date, shows the company what is happening, serving as a basis for management to make decisions on how to allocate available resources, with the aim of optimizing results. The correct use of this tool can assist business management and provide better decisions.

The choice of an unsuitable location has a great influence on the survival of a company, according to Chér (2002, p. 184):

The location of a company is an important aspect for the success of a business. However, this importance varies according to the type of business. For a small consulting firm, perhaps the most important factor is the rental value in relation to the useful work space. For a retail company, proximity to pedestrian traffic and the consumer market and, certainly, the appearance of the facilities

are more relevant aspects. For an industry, ease of access for employees and suppliers, as well as logistical facilities for the flow of production, have a greater influence on the decision regarding the location of the company.

According to Salim and Silva (2009), due to having a range of resources, of all kinds, that are scarce, it is very common for new companies to set up in locations with little visibility to attract customers and, in this case, if sales fall well below forecasts, this could mean the closure of that activity.

The lack of management knowledge is still a problem that contributes greatly to the mortality of micro and small businesses, since most owners of these businesses do not have any management knowledge or resources to hire qualified people. Filippe (2003) states:

Companies that do not have well-managed activities are doomed to failure, as they often know the line of business but do not have the slightest knowledge of business management, especially when the business begins to grow.

According to data from SEBRAE (2004), the main causes related to high business mortality in Brazil are related to management failures in conducting business. Such failures can be associated with other factors, such as lack of planning, absence of market research and failure to identify the competition.

According to Monteiro (2003), small organizations have limited capacity and resources, especially regarding capital (difficult loans and reduced cash flow) and the training of those who work in administration and advisory services, whose skills and information necessary for adequate strategic planning are often insufficient. Thus, in addition to the size of the company, the attitude of the managers also constitutes a barrier to the financial management process.

According to Pandolfo and Veloso (2000):

It should be noted that throughout its life, the company faces the risk of extinction, but these tend to be minimized as time passes. Obviously, this occurs due to the greater experience acquired, market credibility, among others (Id., p. 37).

All the aspects raised by the author are intangible characteristics, that is, they will depend, among other things, on astuteness, market vision, persistence, adaptive capacity and innovation. No company survives without these criteria, no matter what its *know-how* or its dimension of strategic action.

CONJUNCTURAL ECONOMIC CAUSES

The lack of customers is the second biggest cause of mortality in micro and small businesses. This lack of consumers for products is often characterized by a lack of knowledge about how to serve a customer well, and by not knowing techniques to attract customers to the company.

According to Bogman (2002, p. 98), studies carried out by researchers on the subject in question proved the reasons that lead customers to stop buying from a company.

- ✓ 1% for death
- ✓ 5% for change of address
- ✓ 5% for business friendships
- ✓ 10% for greater benefits in other organizations
- ✓ 14% for unanswered complaints
- ✓ 65% due to indifference of the staff who serve them, that is, lack of quality in service (BOGMAN, 2002, p. 98).

According to Abdala (2008), statistics indicate that more than 90% of customers who are dissatisfied with a company will never contact it again and will even comment on their negative experience with 10 (ten) to 17 (seventeen) people in their relationship.

The way in which the customer is served makes all the difference in whether a company grows or closes its doors, because without a good relationship with customers, no company has the slightest chance of survival. Cobra (2003, p. 32) cites some attitudes that can make a company If you run out of customers to the point of closing your doors, they are:

- ✓ Apathy: disregardful attitude of company employees, such as salespeople, receptionists, delivery personnel, etc.;
- ✓ Automation: means indifferent or robotic service;
- ✓ Condescension: treating the customer as if he were a child and didn't know what he wanted;
- ✓ Dismissal: trying to get rid of the customer by disregarding their needs or problems, with phrases like: "we don't have it" or "it hasn't arrived yet";
- ✓ Coldness: when the customer is treated with indifference, hostility, harshness, inattention or impatience;
- ✓ Rulebook: This is one of the most common excuses for poor service, where company rules are placed above the interests of customer satisfaction.
- ✓ Strolling: throwing the customer from one department to another without worrying about solving the customer's problem.

Default (bad payers) is also a major problem in micro and small businesses. According to Mendes (2008), micro and small businesses are the ones that have the most problems with defaulting customers. This occurs because in most of the cases analyzed and studied, these companies do not have the same tools and preventive control resources that exist in large companies. A significant portion of the largest customers are already well served by large companies, leaving micro and small businesses to serve those customers who the large companies do not show interest in, among these are many who are bad payers.

It is common for micro and small businesses to depend exclusively on one or a few customers, which considerably increases their risk of survival in the event of a possible default. For these reasons, the impact of default on smaller companies ends up being much greater, which puts some at risk of survival.

In order not to lose customers, micro and small businesses end up selling on credit without any guarantee of payment. According to Sá (1989, p. 45), “for a business to be successful, it is necessary to control sales on credit: Knowing who you are selling to and charging efficiently is necessary for the success of sales on credit.” He adds that,

It is not enough to sell, you have to receive. Selling well and receiving well are twin conditions in business. Knowing who the customer is begins with registration. Registration is a survey of a customer's ability to pay. When selling on credit, the dealer needs to know the potential of his customer, because, after all, he is going to lend capital to him (SÁ, 1998, p. 45).

As it is characterized as a family-owned company, the relationship with customers becomes close and this can leave room for defaults or non-payment. Remember that this is considered a character flaw on the part of the consumer and not due to company interference.

OPERATIONAL LOGISTICS

Economists call a recession a period in which the economy stops growing. Commercial and industrial activities decrease and, consequently, production and employment decline. As a result, wages fall and people become unemployed, as companies and industries have to cut costs since they are not producing. This sequence of events is what characterizes a crisis.

One of the difficulties faced by micro and small businesses is the lack of an organized physical structure that is appropriate to current regulations. According to Rodrigues (2003), some factors threaten their competitive position, such as: outdated technological equipment and facilities, low investment in research and development, slow and reluctant adoption of

managerial and organizational innovations, and poor cooperative relationships, whether with their suppliers or with similar companies.

In order to be adequate, physical facilities must have all permits up to date, monetary and tax fees paid, and the structure physically organized. For Slack (1999), the physical arrangement of the environment is essential for success, and through it the organization of the space will be defined, where the machines, other equipment and products will be placed, according to the output of each one. Stevenson (2005) comments that the need to plan the physical arrangement arises both during the design of new facilities and when reformulating projects of pre-existing facilities and that there are several reasons for their reformulation; one must always be aware of the restructuring of the operational environment, so that productivity losses do not occur.

Generally, in micro and small companies, the workforce is not specialized, as professionals with more experience end up demanding higher salaries, and these companies end up hiring people without experience due to the limited financial resources available.

Matias and Lopes Júnior (2002) show that the difficulties begin in the day-to-day life of the owner, who, due to a lack of conditions to hire efficient, skilled and trustworthy people to manage his business, ends up accumulating functions, culminating in the inadequate performance of management activities.

Deloitte (2001) says that hiring labor is a critical factor, as businesspeople have structural difficulty in selecting the most competent professionals according to market rationality and objective criteria, and hire family members or friends, who often do not demonstrate the necessary competence for the position, and end up transforming the nascent company into one without a professional management vision.

PUBLIC POLICIES AND LEGAL FRAMEWORK

Lack of credit is one of the biggest difficulties faced by micro and small businesses, whether starting a business or maintaining it.

According to Chér (2000), the lack of credit currently represents one of the main limitations on the emergence and development of micro and small businesses in the world. Brazil, as well as the difficulties in accessing the few lines of financing available for this segment. Both constitute long-standing obstacles to entrepreneurial initiative in Brazil.

Companies often resort to bank financing, that is, financial institutions that are governed by BACEN – Central Bank of Brazil. Among the regulations of the Central Bank of Brazil

(BACEN) is resolution no. 2682/1999, which determines that financial institutions must classify credit operations based on the assigned risk, ranging from 0% for the lowest risk level (AA) to 100% for the highest risk level (H).

Regarding specific guarantee requirements in credit operations, resolution no. 3258/20005 maintained the prohibition of financial institutions from carrying out operations that do not meet the principles of selectivity, ensuring liquidity and risk diversification.

According to SEBRAE (2006), among the main allegations that prevent banks from making loans to micro and small companies is the lack of guarantee, followed by unviable projects and registration in the Credit Protection System (SPC) and SERASA.

PROBLEMS WITH SUPERVISION

The high tax burden causes great difficulty for micro and small businesses. According to Rezende (2010, pp. 47-8) “taxes are classified as taxes, fees for public interest and the use of services provided to society.” Taxes, because they are relevant and constitute “a heavy burden for the company and the market, in addition to the impact on working capital, must be carefully evaluated and considered for effective control in economic and financial management” (BERNARDI, 2003, p. 279).

It is extremely important to strategically manage taxes before starting operations to reduce company costs. One of the biggest mistakes managers make is to focus on analyzing the competition, customer satisfaction, and defining products and services, while leaving tax issues on the back burner.

Outsourcing these tax-related activities is even recommended for entrepreneurs who do not have the skills to do so (ALVES JUNIOR, 2002). Outsourcing is only valid when it is well managed by the organization's staff, and for good performance everyone has to work together: the entrepreneur, the tax consultants and the accountants.

The high tax burden makes products less competitive in the market, which often makes business unviable by burdening production. Micro-enterprise legislation has already reduced this tax distortion somewhat by creating tax simplification where tax payments are unified.

Chér (1990, p. 24) adds that from a tax point of view, “a problem that affects SMEs – especially micro-enterprises – is the issue of the tax bracket, the difference in taxation”, *i.e.* , when one changes from a micro-enterprise to a small business, it is very relevant when comparing the two activities. The author continues that there is a serious mismatch between revenue and taxation when one is no longer classified as a micro-enterprise (*Id.*).

According to an analysis of salary research, the percentage of labor charges in the country is by far the highest in the world, where, for every R\$100.00 paid to a worker under the CLT, another R\$109.00 is collected on account of labor charges, totaling exactly 106.69% (PEGN, 2002).

Therefore, the monthly cost of a company when hiring an employee increases to R\$206.69 for every R\$100.00 of salary. The incidence of this percentage takes into account the total income, that is, all credits made to the employee each month, such as salary, commission, additional payments (unhealthy work, dangerous work, overtime, etc.). This high cost ends up being a negative factor for hiring workers, especially in small and medium-sized companies, and also contributes to the flattening of salaries.

With this surcharge on wages, more and more workers are being forced into the informal sector, and specialists, i.e., the most qualified professionals, are unlikely to transfer to small businesses, as this could pose a risk to their future. These criteria mean that labor, especially specialized labor, is kept away from small and medium-sized companies, either due to risk factors for the employee himself or because this is a very high cost for the small business.

STRATEGIC PLANNING AS A WAY TO ENSURE A COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGE FOR MICRO AND SMALL BUSINESSES

Strategic planning refers to a long-term action plan that aims to interpret changes that may occur in the market, combined with the expectations of each person involved in the process. It is a situation of administrative ingenuity that allows companies to anticipate their work proposals.

According to Robbins (1981), “planning is the advance determination of the objectives to be achieved and the means by which these objectives ‘should’ be achieved. It is the decision of what to do, how to do it, and who should do it” (p.37). It is the most basic of administrative functions, because it establishes the bridge between where we are and where we want to be, which involves a set of subjectivities, expectations, among other feelings (*Id .*, 1981).

Strategic planning, according to Oliveira (2002), “is the administrative process that provides market support to establish the best direction to be followed by the company, aiming at the optimized degree of interaction with the environment and acting in an innovative and differentiated way” (p. 47-8).

Generally, strategic planning is prepared, in the case of macro and *holding companies* , by senior managers, but in micro and small companies where the owner is also an active

employee, it is done by the latter, which does not invalidate it or make it less objective, starting with the fact that it seeks to be highly scientific and objective.

When companies choose and develop a strategic plan for the operation and management of their actions, they tend to ensure greater security in their respective fields of action, because the direct objective of this action is the high reversibility of the invested capital, since SMEs work with limited resources.

Therefore, when opting for the strategic planning system for managing SMEs, the idea is to ensure a direct competitive advantage in the market, making changes that occur in this environment have less impact on the flows with which the entity deals. The company can also seek more solid partnerships with development agencies (both public and private) since it has a budgetary vision of its long-term action plans, not confusing the latter with indefinite deadlines. According to Pandolfo and Veloso (2000, p. 89), “identifying a new business opportunity before starting activities and analyzing the market as a way of verifying economic and financial viability can be a matter of survival.”

What we want to defend through this speech is that with a well-defined strategic plan, the company is better able to coordinate its immediate actions, review concepts, evaluate possible market niches, opportunities and active situations, as well as avoid situations that cause risks to the business.

Due to dealing with limited capital and few opportunities for investment, in different sectors and potential for expanding its actions, each action within an SME must be duly calculated, in terms of not only profitability, but also efficiency, effectiveness, prospect of net return and the time in which this will be consolidated.

What must be made clear is the fact that strategic planning is a management action tool that, if used efficiently, guarantees effective results; which provides security to entrepreneurs and other agents involved in the production and consumption processes.

CONCLUSION

Building a solid business amid uncertainties on all sides may seem like an adventure, but management cannot be understood this way, especially when it comes to micro and small companies that, despite showing themselves to have relative flexibility to take on various market segments, face various challenges, such as market fluctuations and crises that hit them first, due to lower cash flow and circulation of goods.

Micro and small businesses in Brazil represent a proportionally high level of job and income generation for the nation, therefore, the closure of one of them interrupts a chain that directly and indirectly harms an entire industrial, wholesale, retail and/or commercial segment.

As this work has well shown, there are several competitive advantages of micro and small companies and, in the same way, they face great risks, which increases the need for objective asset management, because in the same way they are easier to opening and managing the business and versatility, the imminent risks of closing it are also greater.

It is concluded that the closure of businesses of micro and small entrepreneurs occurs due to a combination of factors and not just one isolated factor. These factors may indicate the final stage of the enterprise and not necessarily the actual causes of the closure. In this regard, micro and small entrepreneurs must be aware of market and exchange rate fluctuations and, as a way of surviving imbalances, seek to act on more than one front. business, for that when one presents low rhythms the other is in a better phase and thus, investments remain balanced.

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